
MODEL MANAGEMENT (MoM) CHALLENGE 2026

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ABSTRACT

This challenge is intended to allow the demonstration of Model Management (MoM) techniques and enable the comparison of submissions, and hence framework/language/tools and their capabilities. The MoM community is invited to respond to this challenge with submissions describing solutions to this challenge expressed in a technology of their choice. Authors should emphasize the merits and limitations of their solution according to the criteria defined in this challenge description. This challenge aims to lay down the foundations of the theory, common techniques, and identify commonly proposed, highly expected, and still not proposed features for MoM approaches and tools.

1 Introduction

Model-Based Systems and Software Engineering (MBSSE) provides a systematic and holistic approach to support the full lifecycle of complex systems. Across this lifecycle, numerous models are both produced and consumed at different stages. These models naturally span multiple levels of abstraction, rely on diverse formalisms, and are supported by a wide range of languages and tools.

Model Management (MoM) encompasses the set of software-intensive activities dedicated to the organization, coordination, evolution, and governance of these models throughout the system lifecycle. Among these activities, *model consistency* plays a central role, ensuring that heterogeneous software artifacts remain synchronized, accurate, and semantically valid over time. Beyond consistency, MoM addresses a broader spectrum of concerns that are critical in modern engineering contexts, where the development of complex systems involves multiple domains, each governed by specific practices and stringent standards. For instance, domains relying heavily on physical simulation require rigorous validation of *model fidelity*, while safety-critical systems impose strict requirements on *traceability*, *configuration management*, and *version control*.

Over the past decades, numerous approaches have been proposed to address MoM challenges, including megamodeling [6], model unification, view-based modeling [12], multi-level modeling [14], and model federation [5]. More recently, both academic and industrial initiatives (e.g., [9, 7, 11, 8, 13]) have led to the development of advanced tools and platforms offering rich technical solutions. These approaches embody distinct methodological perspectives on how models should be structured, related, and maintained, as well as how the associated activities should be orchestrated to effectively support collaborative engineering processes.

Despite these advances, existing solutions often remain tightly coupled to specific platforms or domains, which limits their reproducibility and transferability. Furthermore, the lack of shared terminology, generalized conceptual foundations, and standardized evaluation criteria hinders meaningful comparison between approaches and obstructs the reuse of underlying principles across contexts. As a result, similar challenges are frequently addressed in isolation, leading to duplicated efforts and fragmented knowledge. Notable ongoing efforts include the CASCaRa¹ and AUGMENT² projects.

The MoM Challenge is designed to explore these limitations by fostering a clearer understanding of existing approaches, their assumptions, and their technical specificities. It aims to enable systematic comparison of tools and frameworks, while contributing to the emergence of common foundations and reusable techniques for MoM. Beyond a competitive setting, the Challenge serves as a collaborative forum for researchers and practitioners to exchange perspectives, confront ideas, and collectively identify both established capabilities and emerging requirements for the next generation of MoM solutions.

¹<https://cascara.gfse.org>

²<https://augment.wp.imt.fr>

2 Case Description – Satellite Configuration

The challenge is based on a representative use case inspired by a visit to the Belgian Royal Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)³, focusing on satellite design and configuration. In this context, the development of satellite software must demonstrate compliance with certification standards such as DO-178C [2], which defines objectives for software lifecycle processes, prescribes associated activities, and specifies the work products required to provide evidence of compliance.

For the purpose of this challenge, we adopt a simplified perspective on these normative requirements and focus on two key characteristics that are particularly relevant to MoM. First, *traceability* ensures that all requirements are properly implemented, while avoiding the introduction of superfluous or unrelated artifacts. Second, *configuration management* guarantees the integrity and reproducibility of the system by enabling precise tracking of versions, supporting impact analysis, and facilitating controlled evolution in response to detected issues.

In addition, a critical aspect of such regulated environments is the enforcement of *independence* between teams. This includes, in particular, the separation between teams responsible for the production and the verification of artifacts, as well as between those defining requirements and those implementing them. This separation is essential to ensure unbiased validation, and to comply with certification constraints.

1. **Autonomy of respective activity lifecycles.** To preserve independence and foster trust, existing engineering practices, development processes, and tools adopted by organizations should not be interfered with. Proposed MoM solutions are therefore expected to integrate with these practices without constraining or redefining them.
2. **Preservation of existing formalisms and formats.** As a direct corollary, the tools and the formats they rely on to persist information should remain unchanged. Solutions should operate across heterogeneous artefacts without requiring intrusive transformations.

The context of certification in this use case explains the importance of these requirements. Tooling choices and associated processes are subject to validation by certification authorities, and produced artefacts may contribute directly to the compliance evidence chain. Nevertheless, within the scope of this challenge, a degree of flexibility is allowed: when a format cannot be directly processed by a given solution (e.g., a .CSV file), a semantically equivalent representation may be used (e.g., an .xlsx encoding of the same data).

We first describe how (a minimal and representative part of) the satellite system is modelled, before diving into the Engineering Scenarios that motivate MoM Tasks.

2.1 High-Level Description of the System

At early design stages, the satellite system is defined in a preliminary configuration, denoted *SatAlpha*, which satisfies only minimal functional requirements. In particular, the total mass of the system must remain below a threshold compatible with mission constraints, including launch capabilities and associated costs. An initial prototyping phase produces five artefacts spanning five engineering areas:

Parts Catalogue The manufacturer of the individual parts provides a catalogue represented as an ontology that provides a shared and standardised vocabulary for all stakeholders. The knowledge graph specifies the structure of components and their properties, as well as individuals (i.e., instances).

Bill of Materials Engineers define a system decomposition (or architecture) model that captures the structural composition of the system. This model enumerates the constituent components and their properties.

Network Topology Engineers define a system decomposition (or architecture) model that captures the structural composition of the system. This model enumerates the constituent components and their properties.

Requirements Specification A design requirements specification captures the functional requirements associated with the system, in particular constraints related to component masses that ensure mission feasibility.

Report A report is produced for documentation, human analysis, and certification purposes. It summarizes the architectural elements and assesses whether the global mass constraint is satisfied.

Within the scope of the challenge, a reference version of all artefacts is made available in a Zenodo repository⁴. We acknowledge that participating tools may not natively support the provided formats: contributors are therefore allowed to re-implement these artefacts using alternative formats, notations, or languages, provided that semantic equivalence is preserved. Re-implemented artefacts may be contributed to the GitHub repository⁵ *via* pull requests. We already provide some sample models in other formats, for example .xlsx in place of .csv and .docx in place of .md files.

Table 1 summarizes the correspondence between engineering areas, produced models, and their associated file names in the Repository. Appendix A provides a detailed description of each model to ensure semantic alignment across re-implementations.

³<https://www.aeronomie.be>

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19608752>

⁵<https://github.com/mom-challenge/satellite-config>

Table 1: Correspondence between engineering areas, produced models, and their associated file names. File extensions may vary depending on the representation format.

Engineering Area	Model	Files
Knowledge Engineering / Manufacturer Systems Engineering	Parts Catalogue	catalogue.owl
Communications Engineering	Bill of Materials	bom.json, bom.xml
	Network Topology	comm-network.json, comm-network.xml
Requirements Engineering	Requirements Specification	requirements.csv, requirements.xlsx
Verification / Documentation	Report	report.md, report.docx

2.2 Model Management Scenarios

We define three Engineering Scenarios (ES) that are encountered during the design of the hypothetical satellite system.

- ES.1** The part manufacturer revises the mass of the thruster in the part catalogue, which must be propagated to the bill of materials and report.
- ES.2** The communications engineering team requires a communications-centric view focused on the components under their viewpoint, along with the ability to apply rapid modifications. They want to add a second backup antenna. Changes must be reflected in the bill of materials and report.
- ES.3** Additional members are assigned to the design team, leading to concurrent and collaborative editing of shared artefacts.

We describe the MoM Tasks (MT) needed to support the Engineering Scenarios [indicating which ES they relate to]. Note that it is not necessary for a solution to cover all the below MTs.

MT.1 Change Impact & Reconciliation [ES.1]. The change request in ES.1 consists of updating the value of mass of thruster component T001 from 85.0 to 95.0 kilograms in the Parts Catalogue, while preserving all other attributes.

1. How is the change in the Parts Catalogue detected?
2. Which mechanisms or processes ensure propagation of this change to the Bill of Materials?
3. Is the propagation automatic, semi-automatic, or manual?
4. Can the propagation strategy be parameterised (to happen semi-/automatically)?
5. At which granularity does propagation operate (e.g., element, feature, model)?
6. Can an explicit structure (e.g., graph, tree) be computed to represent impacted elements?
7. Can such structures be composed across multiple changes, and how deeply can they be inspected?

MT.2 Views Management [ES.2]. Views may range from simple filtered projections to fully materialised models. In ES.2, a communications engineer, using a view of the communications sub-system renames the existing ANT001 component *Antenna* to *AntennaPrimary* and adds a new ANT002 component called *AntennaBackup*.

1. Can model elements or types be selectively filtered on demand? On which criteria (e.g. only some predefined elements types like MOF operations, etc.)?
2. Can filtering rules be specified declaratively (e.g., via a query language)?
3. Can views be systematically derived from conformance models? How?
4. Are views themselves typed (e.g., via a metamodel)?
5. How are changes in views reconciled with the source model?
6. How are views notified of changes in the source model?
7. Do source model changes automatically propagate to views? How?

MT.3 Querying & Validation [ES.1–2]. The modifications in MT.1–2 affect the derived value `calculated_total_mass_kg` in the Bill of Materials. As a result, Requirement RQ001 is violated, since the total mass exceeds the threshold of 350 kilograms. The Report must reflect this violation⁶.

1. Is `calculated_total_mass_kg` automatically updated after the change?
2. Which mechanisms or processes support this update?
3. Does it require manual intervention?
4. Can the process be fully automated or parameterised (to happen automatically, or for some cases, kept intentionally manual)?
5. Is the updated status reflected in the Report?
6. Can impact analysis be performed manually by querying all relevant models?

⁶MT.3 differs from MT.1–2: MT.1–2 address *intentional* changes and their direct impact, whereas MT.3 concerns *derived values* that should be queried from multiple formats and *automatically* recomputed to ensure correctness.

MT.4 Concurrent Modifications [ES.3]. Concurrent editing without a predefined editing policy may introduce conflicts. For example, one communication engineer performs the modifications described in MT.2, whereas another engineer **concurrently** deletes the existing ANT001 component *Antenna* and adds two new ANT002 components called *AntennaPrimary* and *AntennaBackup*.

1. How are conflicts resolved: manual vs. (semi-)automatic, online vs. offline, configurable (depending on who, what, how modifications occurred) vs. fixed (i.e. predefined) strategies?
2. Are changes propagated in real time or through explicit synchronization?
3. If concurrent conflicting modifications are prevented, which mechanisms or policies detect and avoid such conflicts?
4. Does the tool support live collaborative modelling? If so, how are conflicts visualized, prevented, or resolved?

MT.5 Version Management [ES.1–3]. The modifications described in MT.1, MT.2, and MT.4 affect multiple artefacts and activities. In a certification context, new baselines must be explicitly defined and justified in a development plan. This task addresses traceability across versions.

1. What is the definition of a “*version*” (single artefact, dependency closure, or system-wide state)?
2. Are versions created automatically or explicitly (e.g., commit-based)?
3. How are artefacts linked across versions (e.g., traceability links between instances)?
4. Can versions be enriched with metadata?
5. Are such metadata queryable and exploitable?
6. Can the rationale for version creation be captured and maintained?

3 Presenting your Solution

This section specifies the expected structure and evaluation dimensions for Solution submissions. A Solution should describe how the proposed approach or tool supports the case study introduced in Section 2, and how it addresses the MoM concerns formalized in Section 2.2.

3.1 Expected Structure of a Solution

Submissions should follow a structured format to ensure comparability across approaches. A L^AT_EX template is provided⁷ and organized as follows:

1. **High-Level Dimensions and Functions of MoM.** Authors must position their approach with respect to the dimensions introduced in Section 3.2, and describe how these are supported by their tool or methodology.
2. **Responses to MTs.** For each MT defined in Section 2.2, submissions must include:
 - A **precise and concise answer** to each question (e.g., MT.1.1, MT.1.2, etc.);
 - A **discussion of alternative mechanisms or extensions**, where relevant, beyond the scope of the questions;
 - A coverage value of NC (Not Covered), PC (Partially Covered), and FC (Fully Covered), for each question.
 - We acknowledge that it might be difficult to present complete answers to all questions in the solution paper. It is highly preferred if more exhaustive answers are published in scientific reports elsewhere and the challenge solution paper is a synthetic version of those.
3. **Replication Package (optional but recommended).** Submissions may include a publicly accessible Replication Package, enabling demonstration and validation of the proposed solution. This may consist of:
 - A Zenodo repository with complete software artefacts and execution instructions;
 - A containerized environment (e.g., Docker image) with pre-configured setup.Note that a link to a GitHub or other impermanent repository is not acceptable as a replication package.
4. **Conclusion.** The conclusion should
 - Summarize the **main strengths and limitations** of the approach;
 - Describe any **adaptations or assumptions** made to fit the case study;
 - Identify **unaddressed requirements or limitations** of the challenge;
 - Provide **lessons learnt** and implications for future work, both for the authors and the broader MoM community.
5. **Acknowledgement & GenAI Usage.** An optional, non-numbered section should acknowledge partners, collaborators, projects, etc. who contributed to the tool/Solution paper; and any use of GenAI in the tool and/or the Solution contribution should be documented appropriately, following the ACM Policy on Authorship and GenAI use⁸.

⁷The Solution template is available in the Overleaf gallery at <https://www.overleaf.com/latex/templates/2026-model-management-challenge-template/mtwngxqjdrms>.

⁸cf. <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/new-acm-policy-on-authorship>

3.2 High-Level Dimensions and Functions (HDF) of MoM

To support systematic comparison, submissions must explicitly position their solution with respect to the following dimensions and functions of MoM.

HDF.1. Approach: The ISO 14258 standard [3] identifies four categories of system integration: *Integration*, *Unification*, *Federation*, and *Hybrid*⁹. Authors must specify which category best characterizes their approach, or justify deviations from this classification.

HDF.2. Technological Spaces: Authors must describe how the solution handles heterogeneity across Technological Spaces [10]. This dimension directly relates to the requirement of preserving existing formalisms and formats (see Section 2).

HDF.3. Relationships: Authors must explain how relationships between artefacts are *represented*, *interpreted*, and *managed*. This includes, for example, traceability links, dependency structures, and version relationships. They should clarify the underlying data structures, their semantics, and the mechanisms enabling their exploitation.

HDF.4. Views: Authors must describe how users may interact with models. Do users manipulate models directly, through views, or both? Can views integrate or compose multiple models? Are filtering, projection, and/or aggregation mechanisms supported?

HDF.5. Collaboration: Authors must characterize the collaboration model supported by the solution (e.g., online vs. offline). They should describe the underlying mechanisms for concurrency control, conflict detection, and reconciliation, and justify the chosen design trade-offs.

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⁹A discussion on, and summary of, these approaches appears in [4].

A Case Study: Description of Models

This appendix provides a detailed description of each artefact constituting the reference version of the **SatAlpha** case study. Its purpose is to guarantee semantic alignment between the reference implementation and any re-implementation contributed by challenge participants.

A.1 Parts Catalogue (catalogue.owl)

The Parts Catalogue is encoded as an OWL 2 ontology in RDF/XML serialisation. It constitutes the shared vocabulary for all stakeholders and is structured in three layers.

Layer 1 – VIM4 metrology vocabulary. A minimal, self-contained subset of the International Vocabulary of Metrology (VIM) [1] is embedded directly in the ontology. This subset provides the formal basis for expressing physical quantities and measurement units without relying on external imports. The class hierarchy and selected properties are listed below.

Classes:

- `vim4:GeneralProperty` – a property shared by a class of objects
- `vim4:GeneralQuantity` \subset `GeneralProperty` – a property comparable by ratio or order
- `vim4:GeneralUnitaryQuantity` \subset `GeneralQuantity` – a quantity comparable by ratio
- `vim4:IndividualProperty` – a property belonging to a specific object
- `vim4:IndividualQuantity` \subset `IndividualProperty`;
- `vim4:IndividualUnitaryQuantity` \subset `IndividualQuantity`;
- `vim4:MeasurementUnit` \subset `IndividualProperty`
- `vim4:UnprefixedMeasurementUnit` \subset `MeasurementUnit` – a unit not derived by prefix
- `vim4:QuantityValue` \subset `IndividualQuantity` – a number and reference expressing magnitude
- `vim4:UnitaryQuantityValue` \subset `QuantityValue`; must have exactly one unit

Object properties:

- `vim4:instantiates: IndividualProperty` \rightarrow `GeneralProperty` (functional, asymmetric, irreflexive)
- `vim4:characterizes: IndividualProperty` \rightarrow `Object` (functional, irreflexive)
- `vim4:unit: UnitaryQuantityValue` \rightarrow `MeasurementUnit` (functional, asymmetric, irreflexive)
- `vim4:isAttributedTo: QuantityValue` \rightarrow `IndividualProperty` (functional, asymmetric, irreflexive)

Data properties:

- `vim4:hasDoubleNumber: UnitaryQuantityValue` \rightarrow `xsd:double` (functional)

Layer 2 – ISO 80000-4.1 individuals. Two named individuals from ISO 80000-4.1¹⁰ are included:

- `iso-80000-4.1:mass` – a `vim4:GeneralUnitaryQuantity`
- `iso-80000-4.1:kilogram` – an `vim4:UnprefixedMeasurementUnit` that `vim4:instantiates` `mass`

¹⁰ISO 80000-4:2019 – Quantities and units – Part 4: Mechanics.

Layer 3 – Satellite domain. The satellite component taxonomy extends vim4:Object. Figure 1 shows the class hierarchy.

Figure 1: Satellite component class hierarchy. Arrows denote `rdfs:subClassOf`.

Table 2 lists all six component instances in the reference version of the Parts Catalogue.

Table 2: Component instances in the Parts Catalogue (v1).

Individual	Type	ID	Mass (kg)
MainThruster001	Thruster	T001	85.0
SolarPanel001	SolarPanel	SP001	55.0
Antenna001	Antenna	ANT001	22.0
Antenna002	Antenna	ANT002	15.0
AttitudeCtrl001	AttitudeController	AC001	12.0
CommCtrl001	CommunicationController	CC001	8.0

Each component instance is represented by three OWL named individuals following the VIM4 metrology pattern illustrated in Figure 2: the component itself, its individual mass quantity (`IndividualUnitaryQuantity` that instantiates `iso-80000-4.1:mass` and characterizes the component), and a quantity value (`UnitaryQuantityValue` that `isAttributedTo` the individual quantity, with `unit = kilogram` and `hasDoubleNumber` giving the numeric magnitude).

Figure 2: VIM4 metrology triple pattern for representing a component’s mass. Solid arrows are object properties; the dashed arrow is a data property to an `xsd:double` literal.

A.2 Bill of Materials (bom.json)

The Bill of Materials (BoM) is encoded as a JSON document. It specifies which component types from the Parts Catalogue are selected for the `SatAlpha` configuration, how many units of each are used, and the per-unit mass. It also carries a derived aggregate field `calculated_total_mass_kg`, which is the sum of `quantity × mass_kg_per_unit` over all entries. The field is derived from the Part Catalogue and the component composition, and therefore must remain consistent with both. Table 3 shows the contents of the reference BoM.

Table 3: Bill of Materials for `SatAlpha`

Component ID	Type	Qty	Mass/unit (kg)
T001	Thruster	2	85.0
SP001	SolarPanel	2	55.0
ANT001	Antenna	1	22.0
AC001	AttitudeController	1	12.0
CC001	CommunicationController	1	8.0
calculated_total_mass_kg			322.0

A.3 Network Topology (comm-network.json)

The Network Topology is encoded as a JSON document and describes the communications subsystem as a labelled directed graph. It is a viewpoint-specific artefact: only the subset of components relevant to the communications engineering perspective is included. Each *node* refers to a component by its catalogue ID and carries a functional *role*. Each *link* describes a directed connection between two nodes, annotated with a connection type and a radio protocol. In the reference version, the communications subsystem contains two nodes and one directed link, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Communications subsystem network topology: one controller connected to one antenna.

A.4 Requirements Specification (requirements.csv)

The Requirements Specification is encoded as a CSV document. Each row defines a verifiable constraint on a named parameter of the system. The schema consists of six columns: a unique RequirementID, a natural language Description, the Parameter to be evaluated (which must correspond to a field in the Bill of Materials or a value derivable from it), a comparison Operator, a numeric Value, and a Unit. The reference version contains one requirement, shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Requirements Specification

ID	Description	Parameter	Op.	Value	Unit
REQ001	Total system mass must be acceptable	calculated_total_mass_kg	≤	350	kg

A.5 Report (report.md)

The Report is encoded as a Markdown document. It serves as the human-readable and certification-facing verification record. The reference version is deliberately minimal: it contains only a heading and a requirements verification table. Each row of the table corresponds to one requirement from the Requirements Specification and records the evaluated actual value and the resulting verification status (SATISFIED or NOT SATISFIED). Table 5 shows the contents of the reference Report.

Table 5: Report

Req. ID	Description	Parameter	Constr.	Actual	Unit	Status
REQ001	Total system mass must be acceptable	calculated_total_mass_kg	≤ 350	322.0	kg	SATISFIED

Template for Submission of Solution to the 2026 Model Management (MoM) Challenge

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Abstract

We contribute a solution to the Model Management (MoM) Challenge 2026 (available at doi: 10.5281/zenodo.19608752) with the XYZ tool / framework.

Describe how your contribution addressed the challenge requirements on a high abstraction level.

Before submitting your manuscript remove the “template” option to hide blue-font notes from the preamble in

Please make sure to submit your solution to the “Challenge” track on the MoM submission EasyChair site
<https://easychair.org/conferences/?conf=mom2026>

CCS Concepts

• **Do Not Use This Code** → **Generate the Correct Terms for Your Paper**; *Generate the Correct Terms for Your Paper.*

Keywords

Do, Not, Use, This, Code, Put, the, Correct, Terms, for, Your, Paper

ACM Reference Format:

Jane Smith, John Smith, and Jane Doe. 2026. Template for Submission of Solution to the 2026 Model Management (MoM) Challenge. In *Proceedings of Make sure to enter the correct conference title from your rights confirmation email (MODELS '26)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 3 pages. <https://doi.org/XXXXXXX.XXXXXXX>

1 Introduction

General introduction of the solution:

- *Why did you chose to take on the Challenge?*
- *What are the general capabilities of your tool?*
- *Since when is the tool being developed?*
- *Is it open-source?*
- *Is it dependent on another platform (Eclipse, etc.)*
- *Is it a commercial tool? Who are the customers?*

*Both authors contributed equally to this research.

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<https://doi.org/XXXXXXX.XXXXXXX>

2 High-Level Dimensions and Functions of MoM

Position your tool in the context of high-level dimensions and functions of MoM as described in the Challenge.

2.1 Approach [HDF.1]

2.2 Technological Space [HDF.2]

2.3 Relationships [HDF.3]

2.4 Views [HDF.4]

2.5 Collaboration [HDF.5]

3 Model Management Tasks

It is perfectly acceptable if your solution only covers some and not all of the MoM Tasks.

To record coverage for each MT question, open score-tables.tex and set the third argument of each \MT macro to one of: NC (Not covered), PC (Partially covered), or FC (Fully covered). For example, marking MT.2.3 as fully covered translates to \MT{2}{3}{FC}.

If an MT is not addressed by your solution, leave its questions as NC in score-tables.tex (the default). It will still appear as an axis on the coverage radar diagram, just at a value of zero. Make sure to mention something like “This task is not handled by our tool.” in the relevant section.

3.1 Change Impact & Reconciliation [MT.1]

MT.1.1 — How is the change in the Parts Catalogue detected? FC if your tool can detect and report changes; NC otherwise.

MT.1.2 — Which mechanisms or processes ensure propagation of this change to the Bill of Materials? FC if a propagation mechanism exists; NC otherwise.

MT.1.3 — Is the propagation automatic, semi-automatic, or manual? FC if propagation is at least semi-automatic; PC if manual but documented; NC if unsupported.

MT.1.4 — Can the propagation strategy be parameterised (to happen semi-/automatically)? FC if the strategy is configurable; NC otherwise.

MT.1.5 — At which granularity does propagation operate (e.g., element, feature, model)? FC if granularity can be described; NC if propagation is unsupported.

MT.1.6 — Can an explicit structure (e.g., graph, tree) be computed to represent impacted elements? FC if an impact structure can be produced; NC otherwise.

MT.1.7 — Can such structures be composed across multiple changes, and how deeply can they be inspected? *FC if composition and inspection are supported; NC otherwise.*

Alternatives & Extensions. *Discuss alternative mechanisms or extensions beyond the scope of the questions above, if any.*

Score.

	Question	Coverage
MT.1	1	Fully covered
	2	Not covered
	3	Not covered
	4	Partially covered
	5	Not covered
	6	Fully covered
	7	Not covered

3.2 Views Management [MT.2]

MT.2.1 — Can model elements or types be selectively filtered on demand? On which criteria? *FC if selective filtering is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.2.2 — Can filtering rules be specified declaratively (e.g., via a query language)? *FC if declarative specification is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.2.3 — Can views be systematically derived from conformance models? How? *FC if systematic derivation is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.2.4 — Are views themselves typed (e.g., via a metamodel)? *FC if views are typed; NC otherwise.*

MT.2.5 — How are changes in views reconciled with the source model? *FC if view-to-source reconciliation is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.2.6 — How are views notified of changes in the source model? *FC if a notification or synchronisation mechanism exists; NC otherwise.*

MT.2.7 — Do source model changes automatically propagate to views? How? *FC if automatic propagation is supported; NC otherwise.*

Alternatives & Extensions. *Discuss alternative mechanisms or extensions beyond the scope of the questions above, if any.*

Score.

	Question	Coverage
MT.2	1	Fully covered
	2	Fully covered
	3	Fully covered
	4	Fully covered
	5	Partially covered
	6	Fully covered
	7	Fully covered

3.3 Querying & Validation [MT.3]

MT.3.1 — Is `calculated_total_mass_kg` automatically updated after the change? *FC if automatic update is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.3.2 — Which mechanisms or processes support this update? *FC if a concrete mechanism is described; NC otherwise.*

MT.3.3 — Does it require manual intervention? *FC if no manual intervention is needed; PC if partially manual; NC if fully manual or unsupported.*

MT.3.4 — Can the process be fully automated or parameterised? *FC if automation is configurable; NC otherwise.*

MT.3.5 — Is the updated status reflected in the Report? *FC if the Report is updated accordingly; NC otherwise.*

MT.3.6 — Can impact analysis be performed manually by querying all relevant models? *FC if cross-model querying is supported; NC otherwise.*

Alternatives & Extensions. *Discuss alternative mechanisms or extensions beyond the scope of the questions above, if any.*

Score.

	Question	Coverage
MT.3	1	Not covered
	2	Not covered
	3	Not covered
	4	Fully covered
	5	Fully covered
	6	Not covered

3.4 Concurrent Modifications [MT.4]

MT.4.1 — How are conflicts resolved: manual vs. (semi-)automatic, online vs. offline, configurable vs. fixed strategies? *FC if a conflict resolution strategy is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.4.2 — Are changes propagated in real time or through explicit synchronization? *FC if propagation mode is described; NC if concurrent editing is unsupported.*

MT.4.3 — If concurrent conflicting modifications are prevented, which mechanisms or policies detect and avoid such conflicts? *FC if prevention mechanisms are described; NC if neither prevention nor resolution is supported.*

MT.4.4 — Does the tool support live collaborative modelling? If so, how are conflicts visualized, prevented, or resolved? *FC if live collaboration is supported; NC otherwise.*

Alternatives & Extensions. *Discuss alternative mechanisms or extensions beyond the scope of the questions above, if any.*

Score.

	Question	Coverage
MT.4	1	Not covered
	2	Fully covered
	3	Fully covered
	4	Partially covered

3.5 Version Management [MT.5]

MT.5.1 — What is the definition of a “version” (single artefact, dependency closure, or system-wide state)? *FC if the notion of version is clearly defined; NC otherwise.*

MT.5.2 — Are versions created automatically or explicitly (e.g., commit-based)? *FC if version creation is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.5.3 — How are artefacts linked across versions (e.g., traceability links between instances)? *FC if cross-version linking is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.5.4 — Can versions be enriched with metadata? *FC if metadata attachment is supported; NC otherwise.*

MT.5.5 — Are such metadata queryable and exploitable? *FC if metadata can be queried; NC otherwise.*

MT.5.6 — Can the rationale for version creation be captured and maintained? *FC if rationale capture is supported; NC otherwise.*

Alternatives & Extensions. Discuss alternative mechanisms or extensions beyond the scope of the questions above, if any.

Score.

	Question	Coverage
MT.5	1	Fully covered
	2	Not covered
	3	Not covered
	4	Partially covered
	5	Fully covered

4 Replication Package (Optional)

We recommend authors provide a replication package to accompany their solution. Simple impermanent links to the source code are not acceptable. Consider using technologies like containerization, notebooks, etc. in order to enhance the replicability of your solution, and deposit them on platforms with some kind of guarantee of permanence like Zenodo. Ensure you provide complete instructions for not just initializing your tool, but also to reproduce the Engineering Scenarios (ES) described in the Challenge.

5 Conclusion

- Summarize the **main strengths and limitations** of the approach;
- Describe any **adaptations or assumptions** made to fit the Case Study;
- Identify **unaddressed requirements or limitations** of the challenge;
- Provide **lessons learnt** and implications for future work, both for the authors and the broader MoM community.

Acknowledgments

To XX for YY.

References

A Coverage Summary

